

A Final Theory That Could Be Even Wrong – The 8-Theory

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Abstract:

The following is an essay on the new framework that predicted the fine structure constant out of theoretical framework of General relativity, a varying manifold invoked stationary. The framework is the 8-theory. The paper revolves around the most significant features of the theory, its testable predictions regarding coupling constants and families below first generation.

Introduction

Ever since the second half of the 20-th century scientists are searching for the solution of the enigma called dark matter. That is just an example to broad, more general Phenomena; we can do it with almost any topic. The mindset toward approaching such questions is leaving some of the most important questions unanswered. If physicists assume that there is certain kind of new particle called "Axion", and that is their leading hypothesis, than they have avoided the equally more important question that left unanswered: **Why there are only three families?** That is the main point of this paper. A final theory of physics should reason each arbitrary number, which appears in it. An arbitrary number that appears in a theory with no reason is a major setback and make the theory much less valid and profound. The question above is just an example, there are many questions which do not get the right amount of focus, such as "**Why there are only four forces?**" same for the question of dimensions. Its becomes evident that modern theories are bad in a sense that they do not have an answer to such questions. These are much more important than any solution of equation of motion. These questions are much more profound. Motion vary, motion becomes very complicated at large scale, no one can solve The Schrodinger equation for more than two electrons, but the amount of bosons is constant (in those theories), the magnitudes is a constant number, families form constant group of three (in those theories) and those numbers left unexplained. String theory has no answer; quantum field theory has no answer. They are not even close. The only theory suggesting an answer is the 8-theory, with regard to two of those questions – the coupling constants and the families' question. It predicts two distinct infinite series to each. Infinite coupling constants with decreasing magnitudes by the primordial equation. In addition, endless succession of families forming below first generation with lighter and lighter masses, that converge to zero very quickly. Next family total mass should be 0.113 Mev. All of the ideas of the 8T are encompassed in few simple equations.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.53)$$

We only need one equation for correlating dark energy and flatness, infinite coupling constants isomorphic to prime numbers or one and many other features we know to be correct. Among them particle wave duality, the intersection of the interactions at $24+2$ as two examples. This framework is leading by far compared any other theory both in reasoning and in prediction, take as an example the primorial. In equations (1.4) to (1.43). Another point in context of the primorial, 8Γ has two arbitrary numbers less than any other theory and it is very simple. It does not have to explain why only four forces or three families, it can easily answer such a question, and the answer is there **is not**.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.43)$$

It is superior for another reason, it provides numerous testable predictions at the energy levels we can reach for today, regarding families below first generation, regarding the magnitude of coupling constants, as two examples. Such a feature is most significant in a candidate for a final theory. As Pauli once said, "It isn't right – it is not even wrong" the 8-theory finally gives us predictions that could be even wrong, which is exciting and interesting, it does so by using only one equation and two conditions, which encompass the entire standard model.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

We have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor, causing matter to cluster:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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